

Common Grammatical Errors Made by First-Year TESL Students in Writing: A Case Study

¹Jasmina Annie George, ²Muhammad Iqbal Hakim Bin Mohd Halimb

Management and Science University, Malaysia

*Corresponding author. E-mail: jasmina@msu.edu.my

ABSTRACT

Objectives: This research aims to determine the most frequent grammatical errors made by first-year TESL students in their writing process and the most frequently observed forms of grammar errors.

Method: A purposive sample technique was used to choose twenty respondents for this investigation. The participants were required to write a structured essay of 500 words.

Findings: After analysing the texts, the resulting data were tabulated using statistical data. The study revealed that the most common grammatical errors made by the participants involved nouns, followed by determiners and verbs.

Discussion: Numerous examples were provided to indicate that participants had difficulty with possessive nouns and singular and plural forms of nouns. Specific determiners were misused, most notably the articles 'a', 'an', and 'the'. Finally, errors based on verbs are the third most common type of grammatical error. The has-have verb and subject-verb links were a source of contention for participants. Furthermore, there are rare cases of tenses errors observed.

Conclusion: research will aid in developing a comprehensive curriculum that will assist learners in increasing their fluency and proficiency in the English language.

Keywords: Grammatical Errors; Writing skill; English Language; University students; Higher Education.

INTRODUCTION

English today has become the second most spoken language in the world. The importance of English has redefined social hierarchy in certain countries. English communication has long been the de facto standard for individuals entering the workforce. According to James (2013), the English dominated the science and technology industries. English is the widely accepted language for people seeking employment in the white-collar and, to a lesser extent, blue-collar sectors. There is widespread agreement that English is necessary for Malaysia and should be accepted as a second language. This is mainly because Malaysia's economy is growing and has moved outside the agricultural-based economy's traditional boundaries to compete in the export and import-based economies. This has resulted in the idea that graduates or students in Malaysia should be fluent in English. English has been taught in school from the age of 5 up until tertiary education.

Grammar is a fundamental concept in any language. It explores a language's structure and how words and phrases are combined to produce sentences (Canale & Swain, 1980). Grammar is the collection of linguistic rules and standards. The impact of grammar on English language learning has been debated for decades (Kumar, Kumar, & Sagar, 2015). However, grammar

does play a prominent role in second language acquisition. Language learning involves acquiring four basic skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. So, it is impossible to speak English correctly without employing grammar. To be communicative, Canale and Swain (1980) claim for grammatical competence. One cannot speak without a basic grasp of grammar. Among the four essential skills in language learning, writing has been observed to be the most difficult (Walsh, 2010). Malaysian students are expected to be able to converse and write in English flawlessly.

Many students struggle with writing; teachers should emphasise basic grammatical concepts (Chin, 2000). Separating grammar and writing education does not improve students' writing abilities, according to an early 1960s study (Braddock et al., 1963; Hillocks, 1986, cited in Chin, 2000). Studies show that strict grammar training does not generalise to increasing complexity compositional components. According to Shaughnessy (1977), the ideal grammar education maximises return on investment with minimal time. She advises teachers to assist teenagers to edit their work. She also warns teachers against relying solely on grammatical language at the expense of conceptual understanding.

Essay writing is becoming more vital in the Malaysian ESL classroom. Despite continuous learning and exposure to the English language, students from tertiary-level education still have problems with the grammatical aspect of the language (Chanranjit, Amreet, Nur, and Thilaga, 2017). This is clear, especially in their written work, as various forms of grammatical inaccuracy appear constantly. Strategies are needed to improve their grammatical proficiency. Numerous research has been done on the problems we face right now, but little work has the necessary solutions to improve the predicament.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

To ensure that this research is dependable and relevant, the author has prepared research objectives. The research objectives are:

- 1) To identify the most frequent grammatical errors in the written work of TESL students.
- 2) To investigate three significant types of grammar errors made by TESL students in their written work.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To achieve a desirable outcome, the author has prepared research questions. These research questions guide the author to streamline and focus on achieving the objectives. The research questions are:

- 1) What are the common grammatical errors made by TESL students in their written work?
- 2) What are the three major types of grammatical errors made by TESL students in their written work?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Grammar is the linguistic component that is most frequently taught to TESL students. Learners should, however, be aware of common errors. It is also beneficial for teachers to comprehend the root causes of learners' errors. If English teachers use proper grammar techniques, they may teach writing skills. Teachers should evaluate and be creative to help students enhance their writing skills. This would be relevant to the writing topic. Teachers should emphasise the grammatical components that influence their students' writing abilities. Individual students should be tested on their ability to apply grammatical principles.

This study may benefit curriculum and syllabus designers because it focuses on the grammatical aspects children must master in school. Additionally, educational book publishers

might develop grammar books focusing on specific grammatical components. This is because learners struggle with a variety of distinct grammatical characteristics. Additionally, students could use high-quality workbooks or other materials to improve their grammar.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The most frequently used theory in Second Language Acquisition is error analysis. It compares the acquired norms of the learners to the target language standards and elucidates reported errors (James, 2013). In language teaching and learning, error analysis analyses inappropriate forms produced by a language learner. It is "the study of what people do not know and their attempts to cope with their ignorance" (James 2013, p. 62).

Regardless of the sample size, the objective of this case study is to identify the grammatical errors in the language acquired by the TESL students. Krashen (1982) established a model that considers a variety of variables affecting language acquisition and proficiency. Krashen developed the Second Language Acquisition Hypothesis that helped bridge the gap between theories and applied research. One of these hypotheses was the Acquisition-Learning Hypothesis. This hypothesis explains that language acquisition is a subconscious process. The learners may not have realised that they have gained language inputs but are aware that they can communicate better in the target language. This is often attributed to the feeling of correctness when using a particular phrase in its correct context.

Another explanation of this hypothesis is that adults learn a language instead of acquiring them. This is meant by physically learning the target language. While some theorists believed that only children could 'acquire' language, this is not the case for Krashen's hypothesis. He stated that adults can learn and still retain their acquisition skills even after puberty.

While error correction has a negligible influence on subconscious acquisition, it is beneficial for conscious learning. (Krashen 1982). Hence, discovering the errors made by the learners could be advantageous in developing learner's language proficiency. Language teaching technique is influenced by intuitions, concepts, and applied linguistic research. Krashen (1982) advocates incorporating these elements into the development of language teaching methodologies. As a result, he developed educational approaches focused on concepts and intuitions. This failure happens because of the lack of interaction between educators and researchers.

ERROR ANALYSIS

Error Analysis (EA) is a linguistic approach that focuses on learners' errors and helps educators understand language acquisition. Errors are considered a means to a goal by some researchers who want to identify efficient correction strategies. Writing allows one to assess language proficiency, memorisation, and cognitive ability (Javed et al., 2013). Saadiyah and Subramaniam (2009) studied errors in 72 essays produced by 72 participants using the Error Analysis theory. Corder (1967, pp. 19-27) says the errors are "important in and of themselves". He believes systematic error analysis can help teachers understand what kind of reinforcement is needed. This study has revealed how students inculcate the principles of the target language, English. Also, EA helps teachers prepare successful teaching materials by providing information on typical language learning problems.

Corder (1997) also stated that one of the primary causes of errors committed by learners was the influence of the mother tongue. This error was because many teachers and educators used the grammar-translation method to teach learners, especially in the Malaysian context. In Malaysia, Grammar-Translation Method has become a staple teaching method for teachers to

increase language acquisition among learners. Nevertheless, error analysis provides an efficient way to isolate linguistic errors made by learners. This method, in turn, could provide the teachers and educators with a way to focus on reinforcing particular aspects of the language to enhance language acquisition and proficiency.

It is essential to emphasise the study's limitations. Numerous limitations in the error analysis could jeopardise the study's efficacy in giving a clear indicator for syllabus development in Malaysian education. As a result, this study reviews several papers that underline the limitations of error analysis in second language acquisition. In his article *Error Analysis and Second Language Acquisition*, Khansir (2012) discusses the difficulties of error analysis. Khansir (2012) cited Schacter's fundamental criticism of the error analysis approach in his research (1974). Schacter asserts that the error analysis method disregards the 'avoidance phenomenon.' The avoidance phenomenon refers to a sample that does not use a specific linguistic structure or grammatical element. Participants may choose to disregard the target language's structure, favouring other languages with whom they are familiar. As a result, the collected data is unreliable, as it does not accurately reflect the learner's actual linguistic skill. Schacter and Murcia (1997) argue that focusing exclusively on errors can blind researchers to the existence of alternate corpora. Schacter and Murcia (1997) highlighted numerous factors that may affect the effectiveness of negative error analysis. Among them is the incorrect categorisation of identified errors. Error analysis criticised the sampling procedure for being biased.

The framework for this research was established by Chanranjit, Amreet, Nur Qistina, and Thilaga (2017). Even though English is taught in primary and secondary schools, the analysis discovered that Malaysian students continue to struggle with grammatical competence. Yaser and Tan studied *Common Errors in the Writing of Iraqi ESL Learners*. The purpose of their study was to examine Iraqi high school pupils' written speech and grammatical errors. The research technique used in the study is a hybrid of qualitative and quantitative methods.

Additionally, it emphasises the importance of the native language in error analysis. Mohammadi and Mustafa (2020) reviewed prior research on error analysis. The primary objective of this study was to ascertain the most frequently occurring English writing errors produced by Afghan pupils. This study aided in the identification of the most often occurring grammatical faults outside of Malaysian contexts. Perhaps there is a connection between why ESL and EFL students from various countries struggle to write error-free English.

Academic Writing Requirements of Postgraduate Research Students in Malaysia, the author examined Jeyaraj's work (2020). This study identifies the human aspect as a means of assisting children in producing error-free written output. The author determined that peer or supervisor support is crucial for improving language competency, particularly grammar.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Language acquisition is essential for assessing written discourse challenges. Inability to communicate and analyse received information may result from a lack of learning the target language. Krashen's *Second Language Acquisition Theory* (1982) proposes various assumptions regarding learning a language efficiently.

To recapitulate, the Learning-Acquisition hypothesis asserts that two different systems exert influence over the 'Learning' and 'Acquisition' systems. According to Krashen (1982), the Learning System refers to the formal instruction that students receive to master the language. Education might take place in a classroom or at home. However, learners regard learning as odd and impractical. Students gain an awareness of their language usage and structure in this way. The acquisition system refers to the target language's unrestricted subconscious learning and usage. The acquisition system can be employed while listening to the radio, watching a

movie, or speaking with a peer. These measures are not intended to increase the polish of the language but rather to facilitate communication.

According to Krashen's Natural Order Hypothesis, language grammar acquisition occurs across individuals in a predictable natural order. Some grammatical constructions require more time to read than others. Exogenous variables such as L1 background or age do not affect this natural arrangement. This concept suggests the necessity of improving grammar sequencing. This will expedite the learning process by placing a premium on quickly learned grammatical structures. However, Krashen is strongly opposed to a grammatical sequencing syllabus, preferring alternative, more effective language acquisition methods. The Second Language Theory elucidates why students make errors when they are learning a second language. Based on this research and theory findings, the author may deduce why specific grammatical difficulties are more likely to occur than others. This could serve as a model for a more comprehensive syllabus targeted at enhancing pupils' English proficiency.

METHODS

Research is imperative to solve the common problems that we encounter in our daily lives. In its broadest term, research can be defined as solving problems or understanding specific problems we encounter. Nunan (1992) stated that research is a systematic process of inquiry consisting of three elements or components, which are: (i) a question, problem, or hypothesis, (ii) data and analysis and interpretation of data. Different people in the research community have differing opinions on the definition of research and its functions. Seliger and Shohamy (1989) stated that one of the functions of scientific research could be to provide empirical or factual for common sense or disprove what has been thought to be common sense.

This research uses a case study approach to identify and investigate first-year TESL students' most common grammatical errors in their written work. A case study approach was chosen because it allows for a more in-depth investigation of a given topic/ subject. Feagin, Orum, and Sjoberg (1991) stated that a case study is an in-depth, multifaceted investigation using qualitative research methods on a given phenomenon. Despite the widespread use of the qualitative method in many case studies, it is not mainly confined to that specific method alone. Some case studies have used qualitative and quantitative methods (Feagin, Orum, and Sjoberg, 1991). Multiple topics and subjects benefit from a quantitative case study, such as economics and accounting.

This research uses a case study design to analyse frequent errors made by TESL students using writings submitted by participants. In the study of error analysis, a case study is beneficial to the researchers as it provides a method to investigate the problem in a detailed manner. Understanding the problem is the most crucial part when trying to solve it.

PARTICIPANTS

The researchers had easy access to the students, so convenience sampling was utilised to choose the sample. 20 First-year TESL students from a private university participated in this study. The majority of the class consisted of Malay students. They ranged in age from 20 to 23 years old. Their command of the English language was rated as moderate. Secondary school students were taught how to create reports and how to adhere to grammar rules.

THE SAMPLING METHOD

Sampling techniques are crucial for research because they enable the sample population to be narrowed down to the most relevant subgroups. By choosing a suitable sample approach, the number of uncontrollable variables is reduced, which may compromise the feasibility of the research. A purposive sample approach is employed to select respondents for this case

study. Purposive sampling, also known as judgment sampling, is the deliberate selection of participants based on their qualities, according to Etikan, Musa, and Alkassim (2015).

RESEARCH DESIGN

This research was designed to investigate First-year TESL students' most common grammatical errors in their written work. The qualitative method facilitates the case study approach that will be used to analyse the data gathered from the respondents. This method facilitates the error analysis approach to answer the research questions and achieve the research objectives. Qualitative research involves any research that uses data that do not indicate ordinal values (Nkwi, Nyamongo, and Ryan, 2001). The minor emphasis on numerical data allows for more room to delve deeper into the narrative of the finding.

The researcher uses descriptive statistical analysis to analyse the data gathered from the participants. Using descriptive statistical analysis allows this research to provide a compelling narrative as to why specific grammatical errors were made more frequently than others. Statistical analysis allows the researcher to visualise the data collected from the participants. Tendencies (mean) and frequencies can show the rate at which participants are prone to commit to inevitable grammatical mistakes. The percentage of errors from each grammatical element will give a broader perspective on the scale of the errors committed.

Having visualised the data, investigations into three of the most common grammatical can commence. The investigation will investigate the types of errors made by the participants and look into the syllabus structure used during the participants' primary and secondary education years. This will provide the research with a surface understanding of the participants' quality of education from the educational institutions.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

Participants selected for this research were provided with an essay question. They were asked to write an essay about their hobbies. This topic was selected as it was deemed relevant to all the students. It eliminates any narrative that may quote that the participant was not familiar with the topic, which could affect their grammar accuracy in the written essay.

Using an essay for error analysis has limitations that could affect the reliability of the data gathered from the participants. Error analysis, like many other research approaches, has its shortcomings. The main limitation of error analysis that could negatively impact this research is the avoidance of the error phenomenon. Schachter (1997) stated that the main allegations laid against it (error analysis hypothesis) make no allowance for error avoidance. This means that the participants may avoid using a specific grammatical element by paraphrasing or omitting a particular part of their sentence. This could be detrimental to determining the full extent of any individual learners' capability in grammar knowledge, thus rendering this research less reliable.

To mend this limitation, the essay that will be distributed needs to be adjusted to reduce the risk of the avoidance phenomenon. The essay questions will have structured points which the students need to include in their Essays. The given structured points force the students to use certain grammatical elements out of necessity. This way, the researcher was able to see an influx of certain grammatical elements in the sample essays collected.

EXAMPLE OF THE ESSAY QUESTION: -

- 1) Write an essay describing your favourite pastime hobby. Your essay must include the listed points and must not exceed more than 500 words.
 - a) Where do you like to spend time on your hobby?
 - b) To whom do you like to share your hobby?
 - c) Describe what you felt while indulging in your hobby.

It is important to ensure that the essays obtained from the participants were not plagiarised from other sources. The wide use of autocorrect would also disrupt the reliability of the data collected. To eliminate these factors, the answers were in an application called Testmoz. Testmoz's premium version allows the researcher to eliminate the risk of plagiarism and autocorrect using a feature built-in by the software, which disabled the auto-correct on sentences and copy and paste functions.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected from the essays were entered into a table form checklist and described in descriptive words. It was decided to separate the investigation of grammatical faults into two groups: standard and not. In order to demonstrate the following, a descriptive statistical analysis was carried out: The percentage of the type of error made, the mean score of the error, and the error frequency are all displayed.

FINDINGS

Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistical data on the grammatical mistakes in respondents' written work.

Table 4.1 shows the types of grammatical errors made by TESL students in their written essays

No.	Grammatical Errors	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean
1.	Nouns	35	25.1%	1.75
2.	Determiners	29	20.8%	1.45
3.	Verbs	21	15.1%	1.05
4.	Prepositions	21	15.1%	1.05
5.	Spelling	21	15.1%	1.05
6.	Adjectives	5	3.5%	0.25
7.	Pronouns	4	2.8%	0.2
8.	Conjunctions	2	1.4%	0.1
9.	Adverbs	1	0.7%	0.05
	Total	138	100%	

The total number of errors found is 138, taken from 20 written essays provided by the participants. Nouns are the most common grammatical errors made by the participants, with a frequency of 35 and a percentage of 25.1%. The determiners are the second most frequently occurring grammatical error in the participants, with a frequency of 29 and a percentage of 20.8 percent. Verbs, prepositions, and spelling are the third most frequently produced grammatical errors in the participants. Each of these three grammatical parts has the same frequency of 21 and a percentage of 15.1 percent. Adjectives are the next most common with a frequency of 5 and a percentage of 3.5%, followed by pronouns with a frequency of 4 and a percentage of 2.8%. Next, conjunctions are the second least common grammatical errors made by the participants, with a frequency of 2 and a percentage of 1.4%. The least common

grammatical errors made by the participants are the adverbs, with only 1 case recorded in this study and with a percentage of 0.7%.

NOUNS

Nouns are the most common grammatical errors made by the participants in their written work. Based on the essays written, most participants have difficulties differentiating singular and plural nouns in sentences. The participants are often confused about whether to use the plural nouns or the singular when constructing sentences, which shows that they did not fully understand how to use specific nouns.

SINGULAR AND PLURAL NOUNS.

Below are some examples of errors made by the participants when using singular or plural nouns.

- i) "I enjoyed all the time I spent on the cooking lesson" (lessons)

In this sentence, the noun 'lesson' was supposed to be plural because no indicators or articles could point out the verb cooking to be singular. If the verb cooking has 'the' article in front, the sentence would be correct as cooking can be regarded as singular; hence the use of the singular noun 'lesson' is correct.

- ii) "I only have a friend (friend) to share my hobby with."

In this sentence, the sample uses the plural form of the noun friend by adding 's' despite having the article 'a' in front of the noun. Any nouns after the article 'a' will always have to be singular as the article only specify the amount as singular.

- iii) "... from external disruptions such as road (roads), cars, and living beings."

In this sentence, the sample uses the singular form of the noun road' despite having no articles or determiners indicating the noun's precise amount.

POSSESSIVE NOUNS

Aside from errors in singular and plural nouns, this research also found cases of errors when using possessive nouns. Possessive nouns are nouns that possess a specific object. They are often indicated by an apostrophe followed by an 's' or just an apostrophe if the noun already ends with an 's'. One such example of this error is:

- i) "However, after high school, internet cafes (café's) popularity is declining"

An apostrophe at the end of the noun café is essential to indicate its possession over the noun 'popularity.'

DETERMINERS

Determiners are words that specify the quantity and clarify what the nouns refer to. There are multiple types of determiners, such as articles, demonstratives, possessives, and quantifiers. Determiner placements are the second most abundant type of grammar errors in the participants' essays.

ARTICLES

Articles are used to indicate whether a noun is general or specific in its reference. Articles are the 'a', 'an' and 'the' that usually comes before the noun. Article errors make up the most errors involving determiners. Below are some of the examples of article errors.

- i) "I have to prioritise my assignments due to upcoming (the upcoming) due dates" The article 'the' is useful when referring the adjective 'upcoming' to the noun 'due dates.'

- ii) “We usually spent our time outside of (the) school area” The article ‘the’ is needed to specify the noun ‘school area.’
- iii) “... since I was (a) toddler.”
The article ‘a’ is important to specify the noun toddler. ‘Toddler’ is a countable noun that requires a determiner to support it.

VERBS

Verbs are the third most common grammatical errors made by the participants in their written work. Verbs refer to the actions performed by the subject. They can also describe the conditions of the subject. Below are some of the common errors made by the participants when using verbs in their sentences.

HAS-HAVE

Participants generally have trouble when using the verb ‘has’ or ‘have’. Has and have function the same way as possessive nouns, as they indicate possession of an object. However, the difference between ‘has’ and ‘have’ are determined by the nouns and pronouns that come before them. The verb ‘has’ is also used beside singular nouns and the verb ‘have’ is used beside plural nouns. Below are some of the examples of the errors made by the participants:

- i) “I was born into a lucky family that have (has) access to the internet....”
The word family is singular. Hence the use of the verb ‘has’ is incorrect. The correct form of the sentence will be to replace the plural verb ‘have’ with a singular verb ‘has’.
- ii) “... not all people around me has (have) the same interest.”
The singular verb ‘has’ cannot be used with the plural subject ‘people’. The correct sentence will replace the singular ‘has’ with the plural ‘have’ as the subject ‘people’ is considered plural.

SUBJECT-VERB AGREEMENT

The subject-verb agreements have many rules dictating their usage in a sentence. The basic of the agreement is that if the subject is singular, then the verb must be singular as well. The subject-verb agreement is one of the most common verb errors made by the participants. Below are some of the examples:

- i) “Most of my friends shares (share) the same hobby with me”
The subject ‘friends’ is plural, hence the verb ‘share’ must be plural.
- ii) “My studies became easier by browsing the internet to look for applications that assists (assist) my studies.”
The subject ‘applications’ in this sentence is plural. Hence the verb ‘assists’ must be plural as well.
- iii) “By doing this, not only do we share our hobby but it also strengthen our friendship.”
The subject ‘friendship’ in this sentence is singular. Hence the verb ‘strengthen’ must be singular as well.

VERB TENSES

Verb tenses such as the present, past, and future occur more commonly than their noun counterparts. Below are some of the examples of verb tense errors made by the participants:

i) "I'm sure that my hobby has shape (shaped) who I am today."

The verb 'shape' was supposed to be in its past tense as the subject refers to the past.

ii) "I have never feel (felt) regret."

The verb feel should be in its past tense because the subject was referring to the past.

PREPOSITIONS

Prepositions share the same frequency of errors as the verbs, and it technically is the third most common grammatical errors made by the participants. Prepositions are words that are used to refer to directions, time, place, and locations. It is often used before noun phrases, nouns, and pronouns. Below are some of the examples of preposition errors made by the participants in their written work.

i) "... having a bad eyesight due to starring **on** (at) the computer's screen too much."

While 'on' can refer to time and place, it is often used to describe vague time and places. 'At', on the other hand, is often used to describe a more specific time and place. In this sentence, 'at' is a more precise term to be used.

ii) "My hobby is quite similar **with** (to) the majority of people around the world."

The preposition 'to' is used when describing a singular person, and the preposition 'with' is used when the subject refers to a couple of people. The preposition 'to' is more accurate in this sentence as the noun 'majority' can be considered a singular noun.

iii) "... my friends have the same interest **with** (as) me."

The use of 'as' and 'with' as prepositions are dependent on the sentence. In this case, the use of 'with' is incorrect. In this sentence structure, the preposition 'as' is the most accurate. The preposition 'with' can be used if the sentence structure is changed to "I, with my friends, have the same interest."

SPELLING

Spelling errors are also one of the most common grammatical errors made by the participants. Generally, spelling errors are a part of writing instead of language. However, the abundance of spelling errors found in this research warrants an investigation. Below are some of the examples of spelling errors found on the participants' written work:

i) "I did not share my hobby or interest the **any one** (anyone) because I loved to be alone."

'Anyone' in this sentence should be a pronoun instead of the adjective 'any one'. Compound noun errors are common, especially for writers who are not familiar with the usage of the words.

ii) "**Futhermore**, I really like to watch movies and drama

alone" 'Furthermore' in this sentence is misspelt.

iii) "It gave us some moral **vales** (values)" The word 'value' in this sentence is misspelt.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

This research has highlighted common grammatical errors TESL students make in their written work. The most common errors were Nouns, Determiners, Verbs, followed by Prepositions, Adjectives, Pronouns, Conjunctions, Adverbs and spellings. As recorded by this research, these errors shed light on how tertiary-level students, especially in English Second Language courses, were not immune to errors. Errors such as singular and plural nouns, thought to be elementary, were still detected in abundance despite their growing experience in the English language.

The data collected in this research refers back to the participants' early English education. The errors shown to be in abundance were grammatical elements taught during primary and secondary level education. Their emergence in this research might indicate that learners might not receive comprehensive and effective grammar learning strategies during their primary and secondary education. However, this statement requires more intensive research. It is unwise to make assumptions significantly when many variables could affect the learner's learning experience during their primary and secondary level education, such as socio-economic background, academic support from parents, educator competency, and above all, level of exposure to the target language.

COMPARISON WITH THE PREVIOUS STUDY

This research shows a similar pattern to those conducted by past researchers, primarily from the works of Chanranjit et al. (2017). In their research, Chanranjit et al. also discovered numerous Nouns and Verb tenses errors. However, the sampling methods of Chanranjit differ from this study. Hence the difference between the data collected is to be expected.

It is also important to note that the approach used in this research to reduce the 'avoidance phenomenon' might also contribute to the participants' grammatical errors. While this approach might seem biased, it is essential to gauge the participant's ability to use these grammatical elements to ensure that the data collected is precise. The avoidance phenomenon could be detrimental to discovering the learners' actual ability in their mastery of the English language.

Holt (1997) explained that sentence errors from second language learners are consistent regardless of the learners' background. Holt (1997) argued that this is due to the complex structure of the English language rather than the incompetency of the learners themselves. Holt continues to list the standard errors of English second language learners, such as verbs, singular-plural agreements, prepositions, articles, and sentence structure. All the listed were consistent with the finding of this research.

ARGUMENTS AND LIMITATIONS

A student who learns English as a second language is compelled to understand the grammar rules and apply them in writing and speaking. However, it is seen that learners of English as second language find it difficult to apply the correct grammatical rules and are prone to make errors in their writing and speaking. Ignoring these mistakes might stall the linguistic development of these students. A generalisation of errors could be made when addressing the common errors made by second language learners, regardless of the level of education. This generalisation might be helpful when developing a comprehensive syllabus to increase

grammar and other language skills competency. Educators must work together with syllabus makers so that a level of understanding can be achieved and reduce any miscommunication that could negatively affect developing learners and graduates who are more proficient in English.

CONCLUSION

The common grammatical errors highlighted in this study will hopefully be imperative to improve the fluency and proficiency of the first-year TESL students. This study may also benefit the syllabus makers to design a more comprehensive curriculum that would greatly benefit the students and the teachers in teaching and learning the English language. The role of teachers in correcting the grammatical errors made by students assumes great significance. Each student may require a specific approach, and future studies can suggest different models for approaching individual students to help them master the requisite grammatical skills.

REFERENCE

- Agar, M. H. (1986). *Speaking of ethnography* (Vol. 2). Sage.
- Al-Khresheh, M. H. (2016). A review study of error analysis theory. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research*, 2, 49-59.
- Al-shujairi, Yasir & Tan, Helen. (2017). Grammar Errors in the Writing of Iraqi English Language Learners. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*. 5. 122-130. 10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.5n.4p.122.
- Ang, L.H, Tan. K.H, Lye. GY, (2020), Error Types in Malaysian Lower Secondary School Students Writing: A Corpus Informed Analysis of Subject- Verb Agreement and Copula be.
- Braddock, R., Lloyd-Jones, R., & Schoer, L. (1963). *Research in written composition*. Urbana, IL: National Council of Teachers of English.
- Canale. M, Swain. M. (1980). Theoretical Bases of Communicative Approaches to Second Language Teaching and Testing. *Applied Linguistics*. I. 10.1093/applin/I.1.1.
- Chin, B. A. (2000). *The role of grammar in improving students' writing*. Sadlier: Oxford.

- Corder, S. (1975). Error Analysis, Interlanguage and Second Language Acquisition. *Language Teaching & Linguistics: Abstracts*, 8(4), 201-218.
doi:10.1017/S0261444800002822
- Charanjit. S, Amreet. S, Nur. Q, Thilaga. R, (2017). Grammar Error made by ESL Tertiary Students in Writing.
- Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American journal of theoretical and applied statistics*, 5(1), 1-4.
- Feagin, J. R., Orum, A. M., & Sjoberg, G. (Eds.). (1991). *A case for the case study*. UNC Press Books.
- Henning, G. (1986). Quantitative methods in language acquisition research. *Tesol Quarterly*, 20(4), 701-708.
- Hillocks, G., Jr. (1986). Research on written composition: New directions for teaching. Urbana, IL: ERIC Clearinghouse on Reading and Communication Skills and the National Conference on Research in English.
- Holt, S. L. (1997). *Responding to Grammar Errors. New Directions for Teaching and Learning*, 1997(70), 69–76. doi:10.1002/tl.7008
- James, C. (2013). Errors in language learning and use: Exploring error analysis. Beijing: Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press.
- Jeyaraj J.J. (2020). Academic Writing Needs of Postgraduate Research Students in Malaysia. *Malaysian Journal of Learning and Instruction*, 7(2), 1-23.
- Joanna. JJ, (2020), Academic Writing Needs of Postgraduate Research Students in Malaysia.
- Johnson, B., & Christensen, L. (2012). Qualitative research. *Educational research: Quantitative, qualitative, and mixed approaches*, 375-408.
- Kaufman, A. S., & Kaufman, N. L. (2004). Kaufman assessment battery for children (2nd ed.) (K-ABC-II). Circle Pines, MN: American Guidance Service.
- Khansir. AA (2012). Error Analysis and Second Language Acquisition. Bushehr University of Medical Science and Health Services. Iran. Retrieved from:

https://www.academia.edu/29817320/Error_Analysis_and_Second_Language_Acquisition?auto=citations&from=cover_page

- Kumar, P., Kumar, V., & Sagar, N. (2015). Role of grammar in English language learning. *International Journal of English Language*, 3(10), 186–190.
- Krashen, SD, (1982), *Principles and Practice in Second Language Acquisition*. The University of Southern California, Retrieved from:
http://www.sdkrashen.com/content/books/principles_and_practice.pdf
- Laura Krefting; Rigor in Qualitative Research: The Assessment of Trustworthiness. *Am J Occup Ther* 1991;45(3):214–222. <https://doi.org/10.5014/ajot.45.3.214>
- Mohammadi, Tawos & Mustafa, Hema Rosheny. (2020). Errors in English Writing of ESL/EFL Students: A Systematic Review. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*. 10. 520-526. 10.17507/tpls.1005.05.
- Nkwi, P., Nyamongo, I., & Ryan, G. (2001). Field research into socio-cultural issues: Methodological guidelines. Yaounde, Cameroon: International Center for Applied Social Sciences, Research, and Training/ UNFPA.
- Nunan, D. (1999). *Second Language Teaching and Learning*. USA: Heinle & Heinle Publishers. Richards, J. C. (ed). (1973). *Error analysis*. London: Longman
- Saadiah, D., & Subramaniam, K. (2009). Error analysis of the written English essays of secondary school students in Malaysia: A case study. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(3), 483-495.
- Sa'diyah, H. (2017). Improving Students' Ability in Writing Descriptive Texts Through a Picture Series- Aided Learning Strategy. *The English Teacher* XL(1993): 164–182
- Selinger Herbert, W., & Shohamy, E. (1989). *English Language Research Methods*.
- Schachter, J. (1974), AN ERROR IN ERROR ANALYSIS1. *Language Learning*, 24: 205-214. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-1770.1974.tb00502.x>
- Schachter, J. and Mrianne, C, Murcia. (1977). Some Reservations Concerning Error Analysis. *TESOL Quarterly*. 2.4, 441-451
- Shaughnessy, M. P. (1977). *Errors and expectations: A guide for the teacher of basic writing*. New York: Oxford University Press.

- Swanborn, P. (2010). *Case study research: What, why and how?* Thousand Oaks, CA. Sage.
- Tawos. M, Hema. RM, (2020). *Error in English Writing of ESL/EFL Students: A Systematic Review.*
- Walsh, S. (2010). What features of spoken and written corpora can be exploited in creating language teaching materials and syllabuses? [E-book]. In *The Routledge Handbook of Corpus Linguistics* (pp. 333–344). London. Routledge.
- Walsh, M. (2010). *Multimodal Literacy: What Does It Mean for Classroom Practice?* *Australian Journal of Language and Literacy*, 33, 211-239.
- Yin, R. (Ed.). (2008). *Case study research: Design and methods.* Thousand Oaks, CA. Sage.
- Yunus, M. M., Hashim, H., Sulaiman, N. A., Sulaiman, W. S. M., Richmond, R. L., Jarail, S. & Royal, N. (2018). Students' Awareness and Perceptions towards "Pre-Writing Stage" as a Strategy in Writing Directed Essay. *Creative Education* 09(14): 2215–2223. <https://doi:10.4236/ce.2018.914162>

About the authors

Muhammad Iqbal Hakim Bin Mohd Halimb is a final year BTEFL student in Management and Science University, Shah Alam, Malaysia.

Jasmina Annie George is a Senior Lecturer in the Dept of Education, Management and Science University, Shah Alam, Malaysia.